

Supporting Information

Towards the Use of Low-Concentration CO₂ Sources by Direct Selective Electrocatalytic Reduction

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Supporting information

Towards the use of low-concentration CO₂ sources by direct selective electrocatalytic reduction

Muhammad Adib Abdillah Mahbub^[a], Debanjan Das^[a], Xin Wang^[a], Guilong Lu^[b], Martin Muhler^[b], and Wolfgang Schuhmann^{*[a]}

[a] Analytical Chemistry-Center for Electrochemical Sciences (CES), Faculty of Chemistry and Biochemistry, Ruhr University Bochum, Universitätsstr. 150, 44780 Bochum (Germany)

[b] Chair of Industrial Chemistry, Faculty of Chemistry and Biochemistry, Ruhr University Bochum, Universitätsstr. 150, 44780 Bochum (Germany)

E-mail: wolfgang.schuhmann@rub.de

Experimental Sections

Materials: Silver nanopowder, 20-40 nm, with 99.9% purity (Alfa Aesar), 3D-NiCu as synthesized, PTFE, and Nafion from Sigma Aldrich. All chemicals were used without further purification. Potassium hydroxide (KOH) was from Fisher Scientific, potassium chloride, and potassium bicarbonate were from VWR. Deionised water was from a Millipore purification system (18.2 M Ω). The KOH electrolyte was purified by a Chelex® resin column before use.

Synthesis of NiCu: The NiCu catalyst was synthesized following our previously published work.^[1] Shortly, the SiO₂ template was prepared by mixing 10 mL of tetraethylorthosilicate (TEOS) in 50 mL of ethanol with 10 mL of ammonia in 20 mL water and 50 mL of ethanol at 40 °C for 2.5 h to form a silica sol. Next, a mixture of 10 mL TEOS with 5 g PVP in 10 mL ethanol was added to the silica sol, followed by centrifugation and drying at 80 °C overnight and further calcination at 700 °C to obtain the final SiO₂ template. The NiCu catalyst was prepared by mixing the prepared 1.5 g of the SiO₂ template with 3 g dicyandiamide in 20 mL water followed by the addition of Cu(NO₃)₂·2.5 H₂O, Ni(NO₃)₂·6 H₂O in 1:1 ratio, and formaldehyde at 60 °C for 4h. The heat-treatment process was initiated at 105 °C to evaporate the solvent, then at 600 °C for 2 h under Ar, followed by pyrolysis at 900 °C for 1 h. The final NiCu catalyst was obtained after template removal and washing with NaOH, followed by washing in water, HCl, and water.

Preparation for GDE: As a working electrode, a gas diffusion electrode (GDE) was prepared using vacuum pump-assisted drop-casting of the catalyst/PTFE suspension on carbon paper (H23C6, Freudenberg). The catalyst/PTFE suspension was prepared by dispersing 2 mg of the catalyst (Ag or NiCu), 1 mg PTFE in 1.5 mL isopropanol, and 10 μ L Nafion, followed by sonication for 30 min (frequency 37 kHz). The suspension was drop-casted onto the carbon paper (diameter 18 mm) to achieve a loading of approximately 1 mg cm⁻², and dried in air. The prepared GDE was attached to a gasket using Cu tape and the photograph of the GDE presented as follows.

Electrochemical measurement: CO₂ reduction measurements were carried out using an Autolab potentiostat (PGSTAT302N) in a three-electrode configuration in-house designed flow-through electrolyzer cell connected online to a gas chromatograph (GC, SRI instrument). The GC was equipped with a thermal conductivity detector (TCD) to quantify H₂ and a flame ionization detector methanizer (FID_{meth}) to quantify CO. The carrier gas was N₂ and the column temperature was 90 °C. During the measurement, the gaseous products were injected from the catholyte headspace as the top injection and the CO₂ stream (backside of the GDE) as the bottom injection combined with a Y-connector before entering the GC. The flow-through electrolyzer cell was fabricated using poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) by the fine mechanic workshop of the faculty of chemistry and biochemistry, Ruhr University Bochum. For the electrolyzer, the cathode/working electrode (WE) comprised the catalyst on the gas diffusion layer (GDL) and the anode/counter electrode (CE) was Ni foam. The WE and CE compartment were separated by a cation exchange membrane. 1 M KOH, 1 M KCl, or 1 M KHCO₃ were used as the catholyte and circulated through the cathode compartment using a Perimax 12 peristaltic pump, while the anolyte was 1 M KOH in all experiments which was circulated through the anode compartment using the same peristaltic pump. The reference electrode (RE) was a Ag/AgCl/3 M KCl with a double junction filled with 1 M KOH for the measurements in 1 M KOH: For the measurements in KCl and KHCO₃ no double junction RE was used.

We started directly with the 50% CO₂ concentration measurement and went to lower CO₂ concentrations (20%, 10%, and 5% CO₂). The dilutant was N₂ (the main composition in flue gas) and the ratio of CO₂:N₂ was calculated as shown in **Tables S1 and S2**. The total flow rate of the mixed CO₂/N₂ gas was controlled to be 20 mL min⁻¹. Galvanostatic measurements were performed at -50 mA cm⁻² and -1 to -100 mA cm⁻² to study the product selectivity. Each measurement started with a galvanodynamic linear sweep until a current density of -25 mA cm⁻². The potentials were converted to the reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) with iR correction using the following equation

$$V_{RHE} = [V_{Ag/AgCl/3\ M\ KCl} + 0.210 + (0.059 \times pH)] - iR \quad 1)$$

The Faradaic efficiencies (FE) of the gas products were following:

$$FE_a = \frac{n_a z_a f F}{V I_t}$$

where n_a is the concentration of the product "a" (ppm from the GC, converted into vol% by multiplying it with 10⁻⁶), z_a is the number of electrons required to generate the product (two for carbon monoxide and hydrogen), f is the gas flow rate in L s⁻¹, F is the Faraday constant, 96485 C mol⁻¹, V is the molar volume of an ideal gas at 25 °C of 24.5 L mol⁻¹, and I_t is the total current in A.

CO₂RR with low CO₂ concentrations: To determine the maximum CO₂ concentration dissolved in the electrolyte, the theoretical CO₂ solubility was calculated based on Henry's law:

$$[CO_2]_{Henry} = K_{Henry} \cdot pCO_2$$

where K_{Henry} is the Henry's constant of 34.1 mM atm⁻¹ at $T = 298$ K, and pCO_2 is the CO₂ partial pressure (atm) at the gas-liquid interface (estimated to be similar to the pCO_2 in the cathode gas compartment).

Table S1. Calculated ratio for CO₂:N₂ binary gas mix (simulated flue gas) and measured flow rate for Ag and NiCu catalysts measurement

Percentage	Calculated flow rate (mL/min)				Value in MFC		Measured flow rate (mL/min)	
	CO ₂	N ₂	CO ₂	N ₂	CO ₂	N ₂	CO ₂	N ₂
Ag	50%	50%	10	10	1.6	0.66	10	10
	20%	80%	4	16	0.6	1.07	4.17	16.13
	10%	90%	2	18	0.3	1.23	1.96	18.07
NiCu	50%	50%	10	10	1.43	0.65	10.16	10.05
	20%	80%	4	16	0.58	1.07	4.21	16.07
	10%	90%	2	18	0.28	1.18	2.26	18.03
	5%	95%	1	19	0.1	1.25	1.13	19.02

Figure S1. Setup for CO₂ reduction reaction with binary mixed gas (CO₂, N₂) to simulate flue gas at various CO₂ concentrations

Figure S2. Potential (V vs. Ag/AgCl/3 M KCl) using the Ag catalyst in 1 M KOH at a constant cathodic current density of -50 mA cm^{-2} at different CO₂ concentrations (50%, 20%, 10% CO₂, and N₂ balance)

Figure S3. Potential (V vs. Ag/AgCl/3 M KCl) using the NiCu catalyst in 1 M KOH at a constant cathodic current density of -50 mA cm^{-2} at different CO₂ concentrations (50%, 20%, 10%, 5% CO₂, and N₂ balance)

Figure S4. Chronoamperometry, **current density vs. potential curve**, and product distribution of the potentiostatic CO₂ reduction reaction measurement using the NiCu catalyst under 5% CO₂ condition in 1 M KOH.

Figure S5. Dependence of the current density on the potential of the NiCu catalyst at 5% and 2% CO₂ concentrations during CO₂RR in 1 M KOH and the calculated cathodic energy efficiency and CO₂ utilization efficiency of both measurements.

Table S2. Possible involved reactions in CO₂RR to CO

$\text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O} + 2\text{e}^- \rightarrow \text{CO} + 2\text{OH}^-$	CO ₂ RR to CO
$\text{CO}_2 + \text{OH}^- \rightarrow \text{HCO}_3^-$	HCO ₃ ⁻ formation
$\text{HCO}_3^- + \text{OH}^- \rightarrow \text{CO}_3^{2-} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	CO ₃ ²⁻ formation
$\text{CO}_2 + 2\text{OH}^- \rightarrow \text{CO}_3^{2-} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	Overall reaction (exergonic reaction $\Delta G = -56 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$)

Figure S6. Faradaic efficiency of the NiCu in 5% and 2% CO₂ concentrations, the corresponding potential (V vs. RHE), and a pentagon-plot for all metrics of merit relative to the highest CO-selectivity

Table S3. Comparison of the related work in CO₂RR to CO at low CO₂ concentration or diluted CO₂

Catalyst	Reactor	Electrolyte	CO ₂ concentration (gas mixtures)	Cell voltage – Cathode potential	Current density (mA cm ⁻²)	FE (%)	Ref.
Ni-N/C	MEA	0.1 M KHCO ₃	10% (CO ₂ , N ₂)	-3 V	-113.6	93	[2]
Ni ₁ -N-C	H-cell	0.5 M KHCO ₃	15% (CO ₂ , Ar)	-0.75 V _{RHE}	-2.9	>90	[3]
Co-Tpy-C (Co-N ₄)	Flow cell	0.5 M KHCO ₃	15% (CO ₂ , N ₂ , O ₂)	-3 V	-24	90	[4]
CALF-20 modified Ag	Flow cell	1 M KHCO ₃	10% (CO ₂ , N ₂)	-1.4 V _{RHE}	<i>j</i> _{CO} : -23	95	[5]
NiCu	Flow cell	1 M KOH	10% (CO ₂ , N ₂)	-0.33 V _{RHE}	-50	98	This work
			5% (CO ₂ , N ₂)	-0.44 V _{RHE}		87	
		1 M KHCO ₃	2% (CO ₂ , N ₂)	-0.56 V _{RHE}	-25	81	

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